

Nation of Islam

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Entry tags: African American Religion, Islamic Traditions, Religious Group

Established in the aftermath of the stock market crash of 1929, the Nation of Islam is a religious movement that facilitates its predominantly African-American followers to learn how to maintain a healthy lifestyle in urban settings. The movement evolved out of a chance encounter between Clara Evans and Fard Muhammad on Hastings Street, the famous south-north street east of Downtown Detroit where a large number of African-American migrants from the rural south lived due to limited housing opportunities elsewhere in the city. Fard introduced Clara to a set of ritual practices related to hygiene, clothing, and diet rooted in the teachings of Mirza Ghulam Ahmad, a prophetic figure from Qadian, Punjab. Clara drew upon his teachings to overcome dependency on public assistance amidst working as a domestic servant with an unemployed husband and a growing family. Faced by a declining Detroit Public School System, Clara established a homeschool for the neighborhood's children as well as adults, offering an Islamic education geared at overcoming periodic unemployment and the accompanying shame of failing to look after one's family. Over the next two decades, Clara and her fellow sisters helped expand the homeschool on a national scale, with similar schools appearing in other cities in the midwest with a large African-American population such as Chicago, Milwaukee, and Indianapolis as well as on the eastern seaboard such as Washington D.C., Baltimore, Philadelphia, Harlem (New York) and Boston. Since the passing of Clara's husband Elijah Muhammad in 1975, the Nation of Islam has split into two factions: one that abides by the doctrinal innovations introduced by Elijah such as his status as a Prophet and Fard as God incarnate and another that follows Elijah's son Warith (Wallace) Deen Muhammad exhortation to embrace Sunni Islam and its understanding of prophecy and divinity rooted in the Quran and the hadith. These doctrinal contestations however are overshadowed by a consensus among members of both factions that black motherhood is both scientifically advanced and morally upright.

Date Range: 1930 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Nation of Islam in American Cities

Region tags: North America

This map includes: Washington D.C., Baltimore, Philadelphia, Harlem, Boston, Detroit, Lansing, Chicago, Indianapolis, Milwaukee, Oakland, Louisville. These are urban centers in the United States with a large concentration of followers of Nation of Islam.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: The Nation of Islam's various newspapers such as the "Final Call" "Muhammad Speaks" and "Bilalian News"
- Source 2: Writings of Elijah Muhammad such as "Message to the Black Man in America," "How to Live and Eat" and

– Source 3: Various documents published by the Nation of Islam such as the Three Year Economic Plan introduced by Elijah Muhammad in 1964

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ccky.org/wp-content/uploads/2011/06/Nation-of-Islam.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: A pamphlet of basic information on the Nation of Islam.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.noi.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Official webpage of the Nation of Islam.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5FC3jKIke8E>
- Source 3 Description: Question and answer at Halimah Muhammad's book release on her biography of her grandmother Clara Muhammad.
- Source 1 URL: <https://new.finalcall.com/>
- Source 1 Description: Homepage of The Final Call, the newspaper of the Nation of Islam.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://vault.fbi.gov/cointel-pro/cointel-pro-black-extremists/cointelpro-black-extremists-part-01-of/view>
- Source 1 Description: Cointelpro files gathered by the FBI on groups they spied on, including "Black Extremists" many of whom were members of the Nation of Islam

Specific to this answer:

Region: NOI Cities in the United States

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.ulib.iupui.edu/collections/IWDC>
- Source 1 Description: IUPUI Archival Collection on the Warith Deen Muhammad Community of Indianapolis

Specific to this answer:

Region: NOI Cities in the United States

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.noi.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Homepage of the Nation of Islam
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5FC3jKIke8E>
- Source 2 Description: Clara Muhammad's granddaughters reminiscing her life at America's Islamic Heritage Museum
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E9WimhRdsBk>
- Source 3 Description: Play on the life of Clara Muhammad organized by the America's Islamic Heritage Museum

Specific to this answer:

Region: NOI Cities in the United States

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Nation of Islam started as a consequence of cultural contact between an African-American woman from rural Georgia and a Punjabi man from Colonial India on Hastings Street, Detroit Michigan, with both individuals fundamentally transformed by the effects of new technologies such as railroads on labor. Although the Nation routinely arouses suspicion of being insulate for its commitment to developing independent schools, grocery stores etc., they have historically always demonstrated a strong commitment to building partnerships with Muslim and non-Muslim demographics. For instance, the Sister Clara Muhammad Schools (formerly University of Al-Islam) for children between K-12 emerged within a mid-western milieu where immigrant Muslims were also invested in starting a private Islamic school system. Such locations included Gary, Indiana for instance where mosques historically established by the Nation of Islam would go onto serve as spaces for providing religious education to Muslim children of both immigrant and African-American backgrounds. Such collaborations were facilitated of course by the leadership of Warith Deen Muhammad who had reneged his father Elijah's racial theology of white man in favor of discarding the category of race all together in favor of ethnicity. Apart from immigrant Muslim communities, he also reached out to Christian groups as well with whom he shared similar political goals such as social justice. The Nation's influence has been redolent across the history of Hip-Hop as well, with artists such as Erykah Badou for instance producing art pieces such as Window Seat that is choreographed to visualize the Nation's investment in esoteric knowledge as key to black liberation.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Members of the Nation of Islam reverted to Islam from other traditions such as the black Church, recounting their religious evolution as an experience of remembering a past that their ancestors were coerced to forget by the slave system of labor. Babies born to Nation families however do identify as Muslim at birth.

Assigned by personal choice:

– No

Notes: Those committed to joining the Nation of Islam have to undergo a strenuous process of receiving membership into the community. This process is gendered, with girls receiving instruction from sisters and boys from brothers within camps referred to as the Muslim Girls Training and Fruits of Islam respectively. Within such hierarchical relationships, the girls learn to sew, cook, and master other trades deemed key for managing the home whereas the men perform military drills and cultivate a rigid discipline to learn how to protect the community.

Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam does not make class a hurdle for joining the movement although

the movement attracts the urban poor. New converts tend to be the urban poor who are attracted by the aesthetics of "looking good" as embodied by the Nation's members. Looking good entails dressing professionally and modestly. The men are strongly discouraged from letting their beards grow and instead maintain a clean shaven face. The women are mandated to wear clothes that cover their entire bodies. Such injunctions are specifically formulated to challenge representations of the African-American urban poor as undisciplined, lazy, drug addict, and sexually promiscuous.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Converts may join the Nation of Islam at any age and those born to Nation's members are born as Muslim.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Although new converts to the Nation undergo a training regimen which is gendered, gender does not preclude access to the community. Nonetheless, the Nation espouses conservative gender norms, with specific tasks delegated for men and women for raising healthy families. Reproduction is highly valued, with women taught to conceive both their uterus and their minds as wombs. Henceforth, it is foreseeable for women who question their valuation as tied to giving birth and raising a family to risk feeling alienated by the Nation of Islam.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Members join the Fruits of Islam and Muslim Girls in Training, learning key skills in home economics for raising a family without reliance on federal assistance. Immersion into the Supreme Lessons of Elijah Muhammad, a manual that narrates African-American history mathematically, has also been considered critical for aspiring initiates.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam actively proselytizes. Men in the community routinely walk around the streets of inner cities carrying copies of the Nation's newspaper such as Muhammad Speaks and the Final Call and distribute it to prospective initiates. The community validates such efforts by highlighting the number of copies distributed, thus highlighting the extent to which proselytization for the Nation is understood as a form of salesmanship. Women do not engage in such public efforts but nevertheless play a critical role in proselytization through building relations of sisterhood with other women and persuading aspiring initiates to consider joining the Muslim Girls in Training. For many new converts, seemingly mundane desires such as courtship with a Nation's member surpasses theology. Captains of the MGT and Fruits of Islam routinely lead the process of courtship, relaying

interest a boy or a girl displays for one another to the targeted individual.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam does not overtly support policy proposals from any political party. However as a religious group that predominantly consists of African-American from urban settings, its commitment to running independent businesses, schools and securing a community that does not require financial assistance from public institutions, it offers a subtle critique of democratic party and its government-centered solutions to urban ills since the Great Depression. In its nascency, the Nation of Islam was one of the key responses to the failure of state institutions at looking after the citizens. With the stock market collapsing, Detroit lost its tax base that could help pay for the salary of public school teachers. The corporate elites decided to abandon stewardship of the working poor all together in order to save money while unions started organizing the ones left behind. The Nation of Islam offered a third route to the problem of living in an urban setting in the absence of governmental assistance. They neither joined forces with labor unions nor continued dependence on the corporate elites and instead built relations of support among one another, acutely aware they had to look after themselves from now on. That spirit of independence in some ways resonates with libertarian tradition of U.S politics but the latter has often been associated with white communities who live far away from urban settings.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates in the Nation of Islam are considered such not so much due to attempts at making theological innovations since the Nation itself is a reflection of a distinctly African-American form of Islam that addresses the specific concerns of urban residents. Nevertheless, apostasy has in many ways structured the development of the Nation of Islam, best exemplified by the distancing of Malcolm X from the Nation's leadership. Malcolm X converted to the Nation of Islam while imprisoned. He would soon emerge as one of the most charismatic leaders of the Nation of Islam, overshadowing its founder Elijah Muhammad. Routinely, Malcolm X irked Elijah, with the latter once warning Malcolm to stop spitting into the well of water from which he drinks after Malcolm said something in public which made it harder for Elijah to maintain control over the community's followers. The rift swelled however during the sixties, a time period when Malcolm X travelled abroad in places such as Egypt and Saudi Arabia and performed the Islamic pilgrimage Hajj in Mecca. While at Mecca, Malcolm X, as recounted by him to Alex Haley in his autobiography, began reassessing Elijah Muhammad's racially charged cosmology in which black gods were under attack from white devils and a mad scientist named Yacoub created the devil out of the black people in a wicked experiment. The Hajj brought him in close contact with Muslims from all around the world, brown, dark skinned, and white skinned. Startled by the diversity of Muslim communities elsewhere, he returned to the United States with a form of politics that radically differed from the Nation of Islam. While he continued professing as a Muslim and recognized the centrality of Islam to the liberation of African-Americans, he simultaneously recognized the necessity of building partnerships with Muslims and other colonized subjects abroad, as he became convinced that in many ways, the plight of African-Americans had much in common with these communities living beyond the U.S nation-state. Malcolm X's awareness of colonialism as a global phenomenon does not necessarily set him apart from the early history of the Nation of Islam. After all, Elijah Muhammad and his wife Clara were also introduced to Islam by a missionary from Punjab, British sub-continent. However, while the Nation of Islam decided to focus on African-Americans within the United States, Malcolm X wanted to create a more expansive coalition, including people who might not necessarily practice a specific set of ritual practices that classify as Islam. He was in other words a more pragmatic leader who merged his spirituality with a radical

politics of decolonizing communities everywhere. Malcolm X would soon be assassinated far too soon for his institutions to grow into fruition. Some speculate he was murdered by a member of the Nation of Islam and he might have been set up by the FBI which under J. Edgar Hoover had been persecuting black radical politics of the sixties including figures such as Malcolm X. Nevertheless, even though Malcolm X could be considered an apostate of the Nation of Islam, he remains fondly remembered by both members of the Nation of Islam as well as youth, Muslim and non-Muslim who find his charisma and sharp wit inspiring.

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: While punishment for apostates has not been codified in a scripture, apostates such as Malcolm X were ultimately assassinated. However, we can only speculate who might have killed Malcolm X. It is conceivable the culprit was another member of the Nation of Islam. Such arrangements were routine during the sixties when black radical politics was under surveillance by the FBI and FBI often took measures such as securing someone from the community to kill one of their own. To a large extent, the punishment of apostates in the Nation of Islam is entangled with state surveillance.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 17526

Notes: I estimated the population of the Nation of Islam by distilling data from the pew research on Muslim-Americans. The pew research found that around 20% of Muslims in the United States identify as black and although only 2% of the black Muslims identify as members of the Nation of Islam, it remains unknown how many once were members of the Nation of Islam or at presently profoundly impacted by the Nation's contributions to U.S history. Indeed, just an estimate of Nation's members does not capture the extent to which it has impacted Americans.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 40

Notes: I reached the estimate of NOI members in the southeast. Presently, members of the Nation of Islam are concentrated in two cities in particular: Chicago and Atlanta. The two cities are in many ways linked by the Nation of Islam as members of the communities network with each other through work while living in these two cities. In general, the northeast and midwest are important regions in the Nation of Islam but Atlanta and Chicago by far comprise a large majority of the Nation's members.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: While a key scripture in the Islamic tradition, the Quran does not necessarily elevate as the most important scripture for members of the Nation of Islam. The Nation instead lists the polemics published under the auspices of Elijah Muhammad such as the 120 lessons, Message to the Blackman in America, and the Nation's newspapers such as Final Call and Muhammad Speaks. Historically, scholarship on the Nation of Islam has been focused far too exclusively on such written materials as well as texts published by non-Muslim groups invested in classifying the Nation of Islam as political and therefore not religious which includes the correspondences of FBI members. Like theologians, they sought to make sense of the Nation of Islam as a violent political group through doing an exegesis of Elijah's writings. Whether in defense or condemnation of the Nation, such textual sources undermine the role of women in managing the Nation of Islam. While women do not necessarily invest their energies in writing and commenting on the Nation's key tenets, they organize as sisters and often play a critical role leading the Nation's institutions such as the network of Sister Clara Muhammad Schools. Data on such activities requires ethnographic studies and greater focus on seemingly non-religious documents in American culture and history including those pertaining to the history of K-12 education.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: works such as Message to the Black Man in America, 120 Lessons, and the newsletters are written. They are often written under the auspices of Elijah Muhammad, considered the founding figure of the Nation of Islam and a prophet who received his prophecy from Fard Muhammad, considered God incarnate. While the Nation's newspapers routinely highlight commentaries from Elijah Muhammad, they consist largely of written materials created by a staff that worked for the newspaper as well as followers of the Nation. Therefore, in many ways, the Nation's scripture is created collectively rather than limited to the interactions between Elijah and Fard Muhammad.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: If one considers the profound impact of Nation's women leaders such as Clara Muhammad on the trajectory of the community and that we should because Clara ran the operations during the first fifteen years of the Nation's history (roughly between 1930 and 1945) since most of the men, including Elijah, were spending time behind bars, then the stories told and retold across generations of their sacrifices are even more important scriptural sources of the Nation of Islam than the writings published by Elijah.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Notes: The Nation's cosmology collapses the distinction between heaven and hell. Members of the community are tasked with building a heavenly community in this world. Hence even though they believe in Fard Muhammad as God incarnate, they

dismiss high gods as spooky and abstract and ultimately a false doctrine that fails to effect any real change in the everyday lives of poor people.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Nation of Islam attributes each human with the capacity to know the divine by knowing the self. Knowledge of the self exemplifies a key marker of the Nation's theology that gestures to its affirmation of human beings as being fully capable of delivering the scripture to one another. Individuals most well-known for such capacity to devier revelations include Fard Muhammad, a silk-seller and missionary from British India, who is recognized as God among members of the Nation of Islam as well as Elijah Muhammad who is considered as a Prophet and responsible for sharing the messages of Fard to black Americans. Another key figure includes Clarence 13 X, a former member of the Nation of Islam who splinted off and established a new religious movement commonly referred to the Nation of Gods on Earth. Popular among the youth, the Nation of Gods on Earth bestow the status of divinity onto every one. Men are Gods, Women are Goddesses, and both immerse into an esoteric form of knowledge based on numbers and their manipulation to learn a reality that is otherwise concealed from them by official documents.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: While the Nation of Islam regards Elijah Muhammad as a Prophet and thereby arises the ire of some Muslims who find such convictions objectionable having learned that Prophecy ended with the death of Muhammad from 7th century Arabian Peninsula, its commitment to the imminent everyday concerns of African-Americans and rejection of seeking comfort in an ethereal afterworld demonstrates a pragmatism that makes is very possible to consider its Prophetic figures as very human. To put it differently, since the divine does not hover in a world elsewhere and instead resides within everyone according to the Nation of Islam, then it becomes very possible to recognize each one of us as fully human and divine.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Key architectural features of the Nation of Islam are its temples and Islamic schools. Apart from a red flag outside the front door, the temples are usually devoid of any embellishments and ornaments. They are usually small in size and located on urban streets such as Mosque # 7 on West 127th Street in Harlem depicted in one of the files attached below. Most of the Nation's temples were either abandoned buildings leased for the purpose of religious gathering and some such as the Nation's first ever temple in Baltimore were in fact previously used as stables.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam has rarely built an institution anew and instead relied on leasing properties that already existed such as the one attached below that depicts Temple # 12 in Philadelphia which was formerly a trade school. According to Dennis Carlisle, a blogger who writes about Philadelphia's architectural history, the temple also served as a front for gangsters and bootleggers during the sixties which makes it even less likely that it would brandish itself with religious monument or become easily identifiable from distance by the police for instance.

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Apart from the red flag, the Nation of Islam rarely features iconography. However as a religious group that values conservative sexual norms and exhorts its members to dress well and cover their bodies, it routinely critiques iconographies that valorize violence in the inner cities especially as proliferated by hip-hop artists. Countering the gangsta image, the Nation seeks to advance an image of the black family as thrifty, disciplined, and clean. Minister Louis Farrakhan, the current leader of the Nation of Islam, once joined a famous hip-hop artist named Treach from the group "Naughty by Nature" on the Black Entertainment Television Network (BET) to critique the proliferation of violence images in rap music since the 1980's as discussed by Pancho McFarland in his book *Chicano Rap: Gender and Violence in the Post Industrial Barrio*. A separate key intersection between iconography and the Nation of Islam is the extent to which the visual serves as a mechanism for remembering Nation's most charismatic leader, Malcolm X. According to Graeme Abernethy in his book *The Iconography of Malcolm X*, the multiple transformations of Malcolm X from a convict to a Nation's spokesperson and later to an apostate who led his own religious movement with aspirations for a more global reach is best read through the lens of the visual, especially photographs, paintings, and movies. While his movement never developed, his image spread globally through images of him found on T-shirts, mugs, and hip-hop album covers.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The Nation of Islam believes that every human being shares a divine consciousness that sustains life even once the physical body passes away. However unlike other branches of Islam, the Nation of Islam does not conceive a separate heavenly realm where the deceased body transfers from the earthly realm. Instead, it strives to convert the earthly realm into a heavenly one through virtues of discipline, hard work, and self-sustenance. Its critique of traditional religious cosmologies that create a distinction between the earthly and the heavenly makes it similar to other religious traditions in North America such as Scientology, Mormonism and various New Age traditions that likewise appeal to American masses because they enchant the U.S landscape and give meaning to the temporal and spatial dimensions of living in the United States. For members of the Nation of Islam, overcoming the ills of urban life in the United States and racial discrimination in public institutions such as prisons, public schools, and clinics represents a major success at building a divine consciousness.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The mind is associated with the womb, nurtured both after birth and before birth through ritual practices such as reading which pregnant women are encouraged to do in order to ensure that their new born acquire leadership skills even before they are initiated into the community. The mind outlives the body. Upon reverting to Islam through subscribing member with the Nation of Islam, members rehabilitate their minds from a mental death caused by the shame of being colonized subjects of United States who have forgotten the knowledge of their African ancestors.

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Notes: One of the marked differences between the Nation of Islam and other Muslim sects is its disinterest in an afterlife. Founding figures such as Elijah Muhammad and others were brought up in black churches, often children of black pastors who read biblical scriptures about finding liberation in an afterlife. However in the aftermath of the great depression, churches no longer had the financial muscle to look after their congregants and one of the alternatives to the black church was the Nation of Islam. Instead of seeking liberation in an afterlife, the Nation of Islam exhorted African-Americans to find liberation now and right here through various ritual practices related to diet, dress, and work that would cleanse both the body and the mind. Hence even though the Nation of Islam organizes funerals for the deceased and remembers its ancestors as one would expect from members of any community, religious or not, they do not necessarily grieve the passing away in a manner that suggests they seek to meet their loved ones again in an other world and instead get back to organizing, since they invest squarely in the present life.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Members of the Nation of Islam do not believe in reincarnation. The body upon death dissolves and while the spirit lives on to guide the living and kinship therefore remains strong through remembering those who passed away, they deceased are not expected to return to the earthly realm in a different form. In its rejection of reincarnation, the Nation of Islam shares in common with other Muslim traditions that also do not associate the human body with any other form.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The bodies of the adherents are buried expediently after they pass away as done in other Islamic funerals. At Elijah Muhammad's funeral, his body was buried at the Mount Glenwood Cemetery in Thornton, Illinois and carried there on a ten miles journey from Temple No. 2 in Chicago on a hearse. A key difference in the performance of grieve from funerary rites organized by black churches was the absence of excessive emotion. Alonzo 4 X referred to such an emotionless performance of grief as an "atmosphere of quiet dignity" that set apart the Temple No. 2 from black churches where congregants may be seen umping and heard shouting during the funeral of a venerated figure. For more on his observations, see <https://www.elijahmuhammadspeaks.com/funeral>

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam bury their dead in the ground, a practice that aligns well the funerary rites of other Muslim traditions as well.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No, graves in which Nation members bury their dead are not embellished with goods. The graves of popular figures such as Elijah Muhammad, the founding figure of the Nation, included a polished white casket alongside the dead body.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: As of now, there aren't any cenotaphs memorializing the ones who have passed away. In fact, even the notion of a grave is absent in biblical and Quranic verses that reference the figure of Elijah, who Elijah Muhammad the founding figure of the Nation of Islam referenced routinely in his sermons as an example of a messenger of God rather than a Prophet. Elijah Muhammad similarly identified himself as a messenger rather than a Prophet. As someone who did not think of his future grave site as far too important, we can surmise he would have been against the idea of establishing a cenotaph for him as well.

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, members of the Nation of Islam are routinely buried at regular cemeteries nearby. Elijah Muhammad was buried at Mount Glenwood Cemetery, located ten miles from his residence at the southside neighborhood of Chicago. Mother Tynetta Muhammad, native of Detroit who joined the Nation of Islam at the age of seventeen and later became a prominent leader of the movement as a fashion designer and world traveller, was laid to rest in the western suburbs of Detroit at Westlawn Cemetery. On both occasions, members of the community accompanied the casket and performed funerary rites such as reciting verses from

the Quran. What makes the funerary rite different than tradition Muslim funerals however is the arrangement of the participants. As in life, they mourn the dead by dressing to the standards of manhood and womanhood as elaborated by their brothers and sisters; the men draped in black suits and the women in long white gowns. Common practices among the mourners that aren't necessary elaborated beforehand but conducted nevertheless include pouring sand onto the casket just before it is buried.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: Members of the Nation of Islam do not bury their dead within an exclusive setting or among family only in a tomb-crypt. Instead, members are buried at the cemetery nearby the city where they were born or spent formative time. They are carried to the cemetery from the temple located in the city and buried alongside everyone else.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam does not bury its members within domestic spaces. Men and women are carried to their burial sites at nearby cemeteries and buried alongside everyone else.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Notes: Although the funerals for such popular figures as Eijah Muhammad and Mother Tynetta Muhammad drew a large crowd, the form of funeral did not differ from the funerals of less well-known figures in the Nation of Islam. The two key rites include offerings of prayers at the temple and the carrying of the body to the cemetery where men lay the body to rest at the gravesite. Markers of formality are the casket and the dress. The casket is picked strategically. It is usually shiny but plain. And the mourners dress as expected in their everyday lives, with men wearing black suits and women in white gowns.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The Nation of Islam believe that everyone has the power to embody the status

of the divine through cleansing their minds and their bodies and following the ritual practices elaborated by Elijah Muhammad related to dress, diet, and work. As a result, they not only believe in a high god but recognize it as deeply anthropomorphic. In Nation's theodicy, God is an energy that resides within everyone, fully accessible and ready to put to use.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam rejects the notion of a sky deity or any form of deity for that matter which is emplaced away from the here and now, the earth and the streets we walk on. In a famous speech that's been sliced and incorporated into hip-hop artist Brand Nubian's "Meaning of the Five Percent," Elijah Muhammad described a sky deity as a history god that was invented to fool the exploited laborers into a false hope for liberation in an afterlife. The Five Percents materialize the Nation's rejection of a sky deity. Established by Clarence Thomas 13 X, The Five Percent Nation of Gods on Earth are a group that splintered from the Nation of Islam and proclaim that every member of the movement is a God or a Goddess. Members routinely refer to themselves as divine or other names commonly associated with a higher power than a human being. As such, they consolidate the very conflation of the human and the divine that was introduced by the Nation of Islam.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The supreme high God for the Nation of Islam does not reside in the underworld. It does not reside in any form of other world at all. It refers to the consciousness of the Black Man of Asia, a figure exemplifying the very genesis of black man and womanhood. Blackness consequently does not refer to phenotype but instead to the very godly qualities that have been for centuries either erased or displaced from the consciousness of African-Americans and Afro-Asiatics across the world who endured colonial occupation from euro-American slaveholders and merchants.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Apart from the gendered distinction between man and woman, the Nation of Islam does not situate the godliness of each member within a hierarchy whereby a high god might be associated or brought into life through a monarch. Even Elijah Muhammad, the founding figure of the Nation of Islam, refers to himself as the messenger of God rather than a Prophet, arguing Prophecy ended long time before him. His example serves as a reminder that the Nation of Islam does not support hierarchical notions of the high God and instead invests in recognizing the presence of a high god, the black man of asia, within everyone from the African global diaspora.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god holds a kinship with every one who belongs to the Afro global diaspora since He or She is black as well. However such kinship does not give rise to a distinction between the elites and the masses. One of the key reasons for the growth of the Nation of Islam in inner cities across the United States is that it attracts the urban poor, many of whom may have decided to join the Nation of Islam due to displeasure with the elitism of existing institutional religious institutions.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is good because he is black. Blackness encompasses all the qualities that mark a civilized man: disciplined, virtuous, sober, and most importantly technologically advanced. It comes as no surprise that members of the Nation of Islam attribute the movement for helping them to learn how to work in a manner than does not make them feel replaceable. Elijah Muhammad, its founding member, used to do menial jobs in a Chevrolet automobile plant in Detroit at a time period when the most valued form of work for a prospective automobile worker was on the assemble line where one was supposed to follow commands and not draw on any creativity and intelligence in the manufacturing of the car. Learning how to resist automation and working through the use of critical thinking and innovation remains one of the Nation's most enduring gifts to the African-American community, especially since the aftermath of the Great Depression and the ensuing decline of formerly vibrant industrial cities such as Detroit.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: anthropomorphic, black, and most importantly residing within everyone from the Afro-diaspora.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: No, the supreme god's knowledge extends into every domain of human affairs: reproduction, education, health, business, and even fashion design.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Notes: No, the supreme God has knowledge of regions across the world, especially regions where the afro-asiatic diaspora has travelled to for centuries. Although the category of the afro-asiatic was constructed and does not necessarily denote a specific community or people, it provides African-Americans a framework for situating their experiences beyond the shores of the U.S nation-state and consequently facilitates a yearning for traveling internationally to gain awareness of the expansive reach of the high god. Malcolm X travelled to countries in North Africa and the middle-east such as Egypt and Saudi Arabia during the early sixties to further his spiritual journey. Unlike him, Tynetta Muhammad, another prominent leader of the Nation of Islam, remained a member of the community for the duration of her life but she also made travels abroad, going to places as far away as Mongolia.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Notes: The supreme high god recalls black ancestry to places beyond the confines of the U.S nation-state but in doing so, it facilitates African-Americans to remember a past they had otherwise forgotten having lived within the U.S. domestic colony. One of the key influences of the high god's knowledge for the community residing within the sample region (major industrial cities in the United States) is a greater investment in the category of the ethnic over race. As a black ethnicity, members of the Nation of Islam have sought to draw upon the knowledge of the high god to configure an identity that no longer gains meaning in relation to its subordinate position vis-vis whiteness and instead finds meaning in the very category of the ethnic that whiteness routinely seeks to shed in order to maintain its privileged position. Materially, this knowledge of the high god as an ethnic black has encouraged members of the Nation of Islam to abstain from vying for political integration through legal means such as electoral politics and reform of public institutions such as public schools and hospitals and instead elevate themselves into creators of institutions that teach African-Americans how to educate, grow crops, and offer health to their own.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Notes: Although the knowledge of the supreme God is critical for the purpose of liberating African-Americans from the malaise of dwelling within inner cities undergoing economic decline, it surpasses across the world. Consequently, even though the Nation of Islam is classified as an American religious movement, it would be naive to assume that its influence is limited to regions within the confines of the U.S. nation-state. Places associated with the United States yet located in the Caribbean such as Puerto Rico and Cuba have a vibrant Nation of Islam presence while renowned figures associated with the Nation of Islam such as Malcolm X and Muhammad Ali have informed the political aspirations of Muslims and non-Muslims abroad. Presently, the Nation of Islam remains focused upon redressing the shame of incarceration, school drop out, and physical and mental illness on African-Americans living within

inner cities such as South Side of Chicago but through hip hop music communities across the world have been introduced to key theological concepts of the Nation, including the idea that the black man is divine.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam believes in a supreme high god who can see in public. In fact, since the supreme high god resides in everyone of us, our sight indexes its sight. A god who lives somewhere else and remains hidden from the sight of the people has been decried in the Nation of Islam as a spooky god advanced by supposedly learned communities that have kept African-Americans ignorant for centuries about the true nature of God. Perhaps one can hypothesize that such a material and worldly conception of God as visible and viewable on the ground arises out of the lived experiences of living in the city. With cramped alley ways, crowded apartment buildings, and polluted air, cities rarely encourage the dweller from raising their head to search for God. God therefore must be found within our immediate surroundings. The Nation represents an example of a religious community that corroborates this insight since Clara Muhammad, the wife of its founding figure Elijah Muhammad, discovered God in the human form of Fard Muhammad, walking on Hastings Street, Detroit in what once was a famous residential neighborhood for the city's African-American workers.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: Since the high god resides in all of us, it's vision does not remain limited to public view. It can see you everywhere, including domestic spaces such as households. In fact, the home represents one of the earliest religious spaces for the Nation of Islam. With the city barring Elijah from holding gatherings at an assembly hall, the members of the community decided to meet at each others homes instead. Clara Muhammad led the community, hosting her fellow sisters and their children at her home as a home school teacher. That home school would evolve into the University of Al-Islam and the Sister Clara Muhammad Schools where children to the present day receive their religious instructions and education.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Notes: Yes, the supreme high god can see inside the heart and mind. In fact, through cleansing the mind the supreme high god prepares the individual for practicing rituals that cleanse the body in its exterior. Pregnant women for instance are encouraged to read to their unborn children, with the belief that doing so would go a long way in making sure the child grows up to succeed professionally. While such insights might also be corroborated by 20th century sciences of child development and psychology, they reveal a deeply religious belief among members of the Nation of Islam that the mind and the body are

inseparable and what binds the two is the consciousness of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

— Yes

Notes: Yes, the supreme high god knows your basic character. In fact, the supreme high god transforms your character, cleansing it through cultivating proper thoughts and behaviors. For members of the Nation of Islam, the essence of one's being is Islam. Every black man and black woman is Muslim. The one's converting to it are therefore deemed as actually reverting to it, remembering a past that had been stripped from them through enslaved labor. Since the goal of the supreme high god is to orient you to your basic character, it knows that basic character.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

— Yes

Notes: Yes, the notion that the supreme high god can foretell the future and guess how people behave is redolent within the Nation's theology as well as Muslims more broadly. The Quran for instance, understood by Muslims as God's speech, repeats on various occasions fearing that human beings have a weakness of forgetting and therefore must be reminded of the truth. The supreme high god within the Nation of Islam theology forebodes the believer of forgetting that Islam is the real religion of the oppressed whereas Christianity has been imposed by the learned to control the oppressed and dissuade them from resisting against control over their labor. Upon remembering this Islamic past marked by black men and women exercising control over their labor and sovereignty over their lands, the supreme high god expects the believer to invest heavily in a politics of self-reliance and independence from governmental assistance, purchase land for growing crops and educate their children privately.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

— No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam resists any notion of the supreme high God that allows it access to knowledge that the members of the community can't receive. In fact, the distinction between the two collapses within the Nation's theology, as every member the supreme high god within him or herself through immersion into an esoteric knowledge that remains hidden from the non-initiate. Hence while the Nation of Islam does affirm the notion of hidden knowledge, specifically knowledge that official papers (newspapers, television, scripture, etc) obfuscate and conceal to sustain the control over the masses by the small elite, it does not differentiate the supreme high god from the believer. Therefore we can surmise that the supreme high school does not possess other knowledge of this world exclusively.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Reference: Charles Lincoln Eric. *The Black Muslims in America*. W.B. Eerdsman. isbn: 9780802807038, 0802807038.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God rewards the believer for recognizing he has been bestowed with divine qualities by the supreme high God. The specific rewards gained include access to a private education under the guidance of brothers and sisters of the Nation of Islam that prepare one for professional development better than neglected public schools in the inner city, access to healthy food grown on farmland outside the city purchased by the Nation of Islam for its followers, as well as midwives and other health practitioners that have historically been marginalized and discarded in favor of modern healthcare system.

Reference: Matthias Gardell. *In the Name of Elijah Muhammad: Louis Farrakhan and the Nation of Islam*. Duke University Press. isbn: 9780822382430, 0822382431.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the supreme high god is capable of punishing especially those who seek material gains without cleansing their minds. Such punitive measures demonstrate a deep suspicion of the Nation of Islam against African-Americans who aspire to elevate themselves to a position where they no longer have to live within inner cities while doing very little for those who do. The Nation decries such fellow African-Americans as having internalized the shame of U.S domestic colony. Their pursuit of integration has been in the past mocked through satire which depicts the black middle-class professional as an emasculated figure seeking pity from white Christian America. One of the main effects of the punitive supreme high god is the persistence of inequality and systemic racism in the United States despite legal reforms such as the voting rights and civil rights acts passed in the early sixties.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam does recognize the possibility of the supreme high god making things happen without directly interfering. At moments when the United States succumbs into a political turmoil and Americans of all backgrounds sense tension, leaders of the Nation of Islam respond by pointing out to the various contradictions unravelling the liberal consensus over American progress. Such moments include the assassination of President John F. Kennedy to which Malcolm X famously responded by claiming "the chicken have come home to roost," thus suggesting that the very violence which President Kennedy had ignored to maintain image of the United States as a bastion of democracy eventually took his own life.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the supreme high god elevates the African-American into remembering his or her past predating the era of enslavement. Remembering that era is supposed to make the believer feel the very positive feelings of the supreme high god: pride. The Nation of Islam has been historically classified as an example of a black nationalism movement that sought to restore pride in being black for the very reason that the supreme high god feels pride as well. Pride functions to offset the damage caused by feeling of shame at being enslaved and stripped from history. To feel pride is therefore critical to overcome all the ills that come through feeling shame. The feeling of pride felt by the supreme high god therefore heals the believer from shame, with the ills caused by shame ranging from physical debilitations such as diabetes and heart disease to mental ones such as depression and anxiety.

Reference: . Islam in Black America: Identity, Liberation, and Difference in African-American Islamic Thought. State University of New York Press. isbn: 9780791488591, 0791488594.

Reference: Edward Curtis IV E.. Black Muslim Religion in the Nation of Islam, 1960-1975. University of North Carolina Press. isbn: :9780807877449, 0807877441.

Reference: Edward Curtis IV E.. The Call of Bilal: Islam in the African Diaspora. University of North Carolina Press. isbn: 9781469618128, 1469618125.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god exhibits positive as well as negative emotions because it is ultimately inseparable from human beings who also display a wide range of emotions. A negative emotion most critical to the supreme high god is revenge. The supreme high god ultimately seeks to gain revenge from the centuries of black subordination under white, as manifested through enslaved labor and other forms of labor since the abolishment of slavery that have had similarly stripped African-Americans the right to use their minds in their work. The revengeful supreme god also awaits a day of reckoning, an end times, when the black man will once again reign supreme and overcome once and for all the shackles of being controlled by a small elite. It comes as no surprise that leading figures of the Nation of Islam such as Elijah Muhammad routinely referenced passages from the Old Testament which unlike the New Testament paints God as angry and revengeful rather than all-loving.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high God possesses hunger for knowledge of the true self that has been concealed for centuries by false knowledge about African-Americans and their religious heritage. The supreme high God however does not consume food fed to him by the believers as is often the case in Buddhist ritual practices where hungry gods are fed rice to keep away the bad spirits. In the Nation of Islam, the supreme high god does not stand apart from the believer. The two instead merge within the personhood of the black man and woman.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam does not create a hierarchies of supernatural beings that are set apart from human beings. Instead, it conceives of the super high god distributed within the consciousness of every believer who overcomes centuries of forgetfulness and reverts to Islam.

Reference: Aminah McCloud Beverly. African American Islam. Taylor & Francis. isbn: 9781136649370, 1136649379.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: It possesses human features. It manifests through the cleansing of the mind and the body. It dresses, educates, eats a certain way to maintain independence from public assistance.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Since the Nation of Islam rejects the notion of an abstract God that is set apart from human beings, it exhorts the believers to conceive of themselves as godly and effect a transformation of this world into the sort of just place that has been associated with an otherworld. As a consequence, the everyday rhythm of daily life seals a relationship between the supreme high god and the believer. The sort of practices one would associate as act of the god communicating with the living in the act of waking up include such mundane practices as washing up and preparing breakfast. Through cleansing the nostril, ear lobes, and the eyes, the believer abides by the supreme high god demanding from him to cleanse his body. Likewise, by preparing a wholesome and healthy meal for the children, the believer follows through the requirements from him of performing black fatherhood and motherhood.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Since the Nation of Islam promised to uplift the urban poor from the inner cities, the supreme high god routinely communicates with the believer through dreams of a better life. The newspaper of the Nation of Islam entitled Muhammad Speaks is peppered with testimonials from new recruits describing how they dreamed about gaining material wealth upon joining the Nation of Islam since its prescriptions for cleansing the mind and the body had made them work efficiently, even for white supervisors.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam has facilitates followers to enter into a trance possession. For many believers, the words spoken by charismatic leaders such as Malcolm X mediated such trance like communication with the supreme high god. While listening to one of Malcolm X's speeches, believers stood resolutely even as it started raining vociferously. Such gatherings often took over multiple blocks in an urban city, and was described as entering into a trance.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam approaches divination suspiciously. Elijah Muhammad, the Nation's founding figure, juxtaposed divination with divinity, arguing that divination usually reduces to mere dreams and such dreams should not be conflated with visions. He cites the Holy Quran to corroborate his condemnation of divination as well. The Holy Quran, he wrote, condemned people who sought to exercise authority by describing their dreams.

Reference: Elijah Muhammad. *The True History of Elijah Muhammad*. Secretarius Mempis Publications. isbn: 9781884855771, 1884855776.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The Nation of Islam recognizes that any one may communicate with the supreme high god but it facilitates such divine encounters through ritual practices that situate prospective members of the nation of Islam within gendered hierarchical relationships with brothers and sisters. Prospective recruits join the Fruits of Islam or the Girls in Training based on their gender and undergo a rigorous rite of initiation that fastens a relationship with the divine through seemingly mundane practices related to acting like a man and a woman.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: There are no monarchs acknowledged or respected by followers of the Nation of Islam. As the name of the movement indicates, the followers conceive themselves as entering a nation within the United States, establishing independently run schools, grocery stores, and even farms. Hence although they acknowledge the political leaders of the United States, they distance themselves from them. Leaders of the community exercise authority for their capacity to organize followers. They include ministers and educators, and even fashion designers, all sharing in common an ability to inspire youth and city dwellers in their pursuit of making a profit.

Reference: Edward Curtis IV E.. *Islamizing the Black Body: Ritual and Power in Elijah Muhammad's Nation of Islam*. *Religion and American Culture: A Journal of Interpretation*, 12(2)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Music. One of the key ritual practices through which members of the Nation of Islam communicate with the divine is music, especially the genre of hip-hop. Lord Jamar, a founding figure of the Five Percent Nation of Gods on Earth which splintered from the Nation of Islam, communicates to God through singing hip-hop. Listening to and dancing to hip-hop music has also played a formative role in shaping the religious piety of members of the Nation of Islam, and many others who were either former members of the Nation of Islam, or belong to Warith Deen Muhammad's reformed movement. Such ritual practices often clash with other Muslim communities that fear that such sensual and bodily engagements with the divine destabilize gender norms, since they facilitate the cultivation of an emotion of cool and encourage men and women to dance collectively. Such tensions routinely arise at major Muslim-American gatherings such as the annual convention held by the Islamic Society of North America (ISNA), which has historically been associated with immigrant Muslim communities from places such as Syria, Iraq, and Pakistan, many of whom might fear the city as a sight of decay and immorality. For members of the Nation of Islam on the other hand, the city is sacred. Its sounds play a formative role in their Islamic piety and those include the sounds of Hip-Hop music and the technology of the turntable which has been used by hip-hop artists to perform Dhikr, a key Islamic tradition that refers to remembering Allah.

Reference: Su'ad Khabeer Abdul. Muslim Cool: Race, Religion, and Hip-Hop in the United States. New York University Press. isbn: 9781479866328, 1479866326.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits in the Nation of Islam are inseparable from the spirit of Allah, the original black man. Previously an atom, the black man evolved into a body as well as the earth, giving rise to the concept of time and space. As a result, everything we can see around our material, earthly realm from sunlight to darkness and roads and mountains are human spirits. Everything seen is human spirit.

Reference: Claude Clegg. An Original Man: The Life and Times of Elijah Muhammad. St. Martin's Press. isbn: 9780312181536, 0312181531.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirits can be physically felt for as long as the spirit of the original black man is felt through moving around our material surroundings. However, the human spirit does not transfer to another body upon death. The spirit instead lives on as knowledge passed down from one generation to the next. A key distinction in Nation's theology is between mental and physical spirit. Instead of conceiving the spirit

as a corporeal body, it associates the spirit with the mental. Prior to the moment when Fard Muhammad taught Elijah Muhammad about the original black man as god, black people in the Americas were alleged to have been mentally dead. Their spirits therefore revived and could be felt through the change in their minds, the ability to remember that godly past.

Reference: Lance Shabazz. Blood, Sweat, and Tears: Nation of Islam and Me. Lulu Publishing Services. isbn: 9781483425825, 1483425827.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: No, human spirits knowledge extend to all facets of human affairs, especially astrological and mathematical insights into the creation of the universe. Every particle, the Nation of Islam, believes was infused with the human spirits of God, the original black man. Followers routinely draw upon the study of numbers to corroborate such spiritual revelations. Tynetta Muhammad in fact even defined Islam as mathematics that discloses universal knowledge and hidden mysteries of the human spirit embodied by God, the original black man.

Reference: Tynetta Muhammad. The Mathematical Code and Musical Notation. The Final Call., 22

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Human spirits' knowledge extends to all the regions around the world, especially Africa and Asia where the human spirit of God, the original black man resided when the universe was created and spread to all regions around the world, including the Americas. Such an expansive geography of the knowledge of human spirit facilitates members of the Nation of Islam to configure an ethnic identity, which they set apart from racial identity, as anchored around mobility and relationship with oppressed communities all around the world. While the appetite for international travel among Nation's followers routinely center around Malcolm X's visits to Egypt and Saudi Arabia, there include many other followers of the Nation of Islam who have furthered their spiritual reversion to Islam by traveling to countries beyond the shores of the U.S. nation-state. These countries include Muslim nation-states such as Egypt and Saudi Arabia where followers studied Islam at renowned institutions of higher education such as Al-Azhar University. Such educational trips have become popular in the aftermath of 9/11 among young Muslim-Americans more broadly. They conceive such regions as reservoirs of authentic knowledge on Islam as more and more charismatic leaders emerge across the Muslim world with contesting understandings of what counts as Islam. Since members

of the Nation of Islam recognize the human spirit of the original black as God, their journey for gaining more knowledge of the human spirit often leads them to great emperors and military general such as Genghis Khan who might not necessarily make an appearance on a class on fiqh and hadith at Al-Azhar University. Tynnetta Muhammad learned about Genghis Khan on a journey to Mongolia which she took in 2002. She found Genghis Khan's military principals as a prophecy carried forth by Elijah Muhammad. Her thirst for identifying a thread between the knowledge of Genghis Khan and Elijah Muhammad led her to all sorts of seemingly secular places ranging from the National Museum of Mongolian History at Ulaanbaatar to a museum exhibit on Genghis Khan at the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology. Her travelogues offers a refreshingly mundane example of how global the knowledge of the human spirit is according to members of the Nation of Islam.

Reference: Tynnetta Muhammad. Recapturing the Mongolian Vision. The Final Call.

Reference: Zareena Grewal. Islam is a Foreign Country: American Muslims and the Global Crisis of Authority. New York University Press. isbn: 9781479800568, 1479800562.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits knowledge spans across the world.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Narratives on Louis Farrakhan's ascension as the leader of the Nation of Islam center around finding the nation in his heart and mind.

Reference: Clifton Marsh E.. The Lost-Found Nation of Islam in America. Scarecrow Press. isbn: 9780810881426, 081088142X.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Elijah's writings routinely label various biblical figures such as Lazarus, Devil, Satan, and God as characters. God, Elijah argues, is a character who is present in the human and made himself known through the human figure of Fard Muhammad to signal the end to Devil's dominion over the world.

Reference: Elijah Muhammad, . The Genesis Years of Elijah Muhammad. SECRETARIUS INCORPORATED. isbn: 9781884855801, 1884855806.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic tradition broadly speaking recognizes tendencies in human beings such as forgetfulness, thus the Quran routinely repeats itself. The Nation of Islam in particular recognizes that with a weakened human spirit, the individual will be gullible to the promises of integration, failing to recognize what the white devil gains from making compromises. In many ways, the Nation of Islam foretold failures of the Civil Rights that we presently see with the rise of a new liberation movement that rejects the ideal of racial integration in its quest for racial justice.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: They have knowledge of numbers that delineate God's role in the world and allow followers of the Nation of Islam to analyze human history.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: In Nation's theology, spirits are subjected onto us instead of the other way around, which means that we are endowed with the sort of infinite knowledge that is routinely associated with a God understood as distinct from human. The greatest benefit that human spirits can offer to us is in cautioning us against being misled by the devil as a guide.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits can punish especially by taking the form of a devil who promises to guide us to God but in reality strives to mislead us. Effectively, human spirits punish us by making us believe in a spirit God that is set apart from man. In contrast, the Nation of Islam believes that God and black man are coterminous, both distinct from the white man whose spirit has cast all sorts of spells on black people into acquiescing to the abrogation of their rights for centuries.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world as exemplified by the emergence of the Nation of Islam amidst a general decline in organized religion in America. Spirit, also known as the ruh, is gendered as a man in Nation's theology, that God breathes into the human being. But in directly, the spirit gives rise to the soul, nafs, gendered as a female, is the reservoir of all the various possibilities for the possibility of evolving. Upon being sold into slavery during the transatlantic slave trade, African diasporas in the Americas lost their spirit, having being forcibly stripped off their communities and ancestors. The violence of losing the spirit however elevated the role of the soul in recreating a community that looks into the future, acutely aware that the past ceases to exist. Read differently, the patriarchal structure of the Nation of Islam empowers women to reconnect black Americans with their God in ways that the religious institutions they were converted into, namely the Christian church, could not. Indirectly, the destruction of the human spirit of all the Africans sent out on the ships to work as slaves, made it possible for women to create a new community with powers they were otherwise denied. I would argue that the progressive era of the early 20th century, with its emphasis on science, technology, and empiricism, helped feminize religion as best exemplified by the emergence of Clara Muhammad whom I regard as more critical to the Nation's growth than her husband Elijah. In the meanwhile, institutional religions such as Christianity suffered as the country suffered from a Great Depression, making churches no longer financially solvent and incapable of looking after their congregants' well-being. There would be no Nation of Islam without the destruction of organized religion. Put it differently, there won't be the soul reverting black urban Americans into Muslims without the demise of the spirit.

Reference: Dawn-Marie Gibson , Jamillah Karim. Women of the Nation. New York University Press. isbn: 9780814769959, 0814769950.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, human spirits have memory of life. Also known as ruh, spirit is the life that God breathes into you. Sociologically, it refers to a community that has a set of prescribed ritual practices, relationships, rhythm of work and leisure that orients one as part of a larger collective. Once the human spirit breaks down, as it did during the forced enslavement of Africans during the transatlantic slave trade, it nonetheless contains memory that one could activate (put into use as remembering) through ritual practices such as singing and dancing. The spirit in other words is a reservoir of memory, offering lens into the past that archives may fail to provide, and it moves when the body moves.

Reference: Sylviane Diouf A.. Servants of Allah: African Muslims Enslaved in the Americas. New York University Press. isbn: 9780814720820, 081472082X.

Reference: Michael Gomez. Black Crescent: The Experience and Legacy of African Muslims in the Americas. Cambridge University Press. isbn: 9780814769959, 0814769950.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, human spirits exhibit positive emotions such as joy when it has not been attacked by coerced migration and displacement.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the problem of redressing the negative emotions of the human spirit is perhaps the most critical work the Nation of Islam does for its members. Members share in common "painfully stored emotions" (Gibson & Karim, 2014, p. 144) and aspire to find their way by resurrecting their souls into action through ritual practices related to dress, hygiene, and education. Muslim migrants, even the ones who do not identify as members of the Nation of Islam, often ascribe the theological and practical insights of the Nation, in helping them emplace in the United States as racial minorities. Unfortunately, scholarship on American Islam naturalizes the dichotomy between "immigrant" and "black" Islam, thus overlooking the critical role that Nation has played in shaping the ritual practices of Muslims more broadly speaking. Examining the history of Islam in America without relying upon such categorical distinctions that emerge out of the academy on the other hand offers key insights on the American component of American Islam. Specifically, as has been the case with non-Muslim traditions in America such as Puritanism, Evangelicalism, Spiritualism and New Age Religions, Islam in America also routinely escapes the neat categorical distinctions between different denominations or sects, and represents a form of "metaphysical religion" (Albanese, 2008) that allows people constantly on the move to form relationships with one another despite lacking doctrinal unity.

Reference: Catherine Albanese L.. A Republic of Mind and Spirit: A Cultural History of American Metaphysical Religion. Yale University Press. isbn: 9780300136159, 0300136153.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, human spirits communicate in waking. Nation's theology corroborates that insight because it describes the inverse in the context of speaking of a community, black diaspora in North America, that has a weakened human spirit due to forgetfulness of ancestral past. Specifically, the Nation describes African-Americans who remain in such a state of forgetfulness and lack the insight that Islam is their authentic religion as a spiritually dead people, by which it means that their spirits are asleep.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Dreaming represents an active cultivation of a longing for returning to a home that was taken away from the black diaspora in the Americas by

enforced migration and the transatlantic slave trade. However, when the spirit is dying as the Nation of Islam argued it had been, then dreaming becomes obsolete since the past can never be restored. Instead of dreaming for a past, the Nation of Islam sought to imagine a radically new future marked by black man reclaiming his divine status. Activities such as dreaming are usually looked upon negatively in Nation's scriptural sources, with Elijah Muhammad (Muhammad, 2009, 93) reminding his audience that white Christians routinely referred to Islam as a dream of Mohammad in their negative representations of Islam.

↳ In trance possession:

— Yes

Notes: Yes, trance possession is a key motif in the history of Islam and African Religions, and the Nation of Islam offers a good example of it. In Nation's creation story, a mad scientist named Yacoub conducts a scientific experiment that goes terribly wrong and culminates with the creation of the white man, the devil. While trance possessions can bring about positive change as in the case of women in Africa drawing upon the voices they heard to exercise authority otherwise barred from them, in this particular case the trance possession was more akin to a frankenstein type of a scenario, bringing evil into the world that sought to naturalize black subordination to white and coerce acquiescence from the oppressed through forgetfulness of black divinity. Narratives of the mad scientist Yacoub are redolent in Nation's scriptural sources ascribed to the writings of Elijah Muhammad but are perhaps popularized more effectively by literary figures such as Amiri Baraka whose staging *The Black Mass* in 1965 reenacted the scientific experiment through mechanized sounds of sorcery that revealed an acute awareness of how the Nation built on an African belief in trance possession to offer a critique of the ways in which the growing mechanization of work in the United States were destroying black communities.

Reference: Stephen Wehmeyer C.. *Conjuration Contractions: Techno-Hermeneutics, Mechanical Wizardry, and the Material Culture of African American Folk Magic.* (Hugh Page , Margarita Guillory , Stephen Finley, Ed.), Esotericism in African American Religious Experience. BRILL. isbn: 9789004283428, 9004283420.

↳ Through divination processes:

— Yes

Notes: One can describe Elijah Muhammad as a diviner who shared with African-Americans the true knowledge of God, the original black man.

↳ Only through specialists:

— No

Notes: There are various ritual practices that allow one to communicate with the human spirits but these practices are not exclusive to specialists. To the contrary, the Nation seeks to make everyone from the black diaspora to communicate with the human spirits, knowing that the forced displacement

of Africans due to the transatlantic slave trade has severed it.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam does not idealize a monarchy. The U.S. domestic colony, although not a monarchy, has been castigated by the Nation's followers for giving false dreams of integration at the expense of further severing the ties of black diasporas with the human spirits. Hence the most effective model of governance for communicating with the human spirits is a self-governance.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: For members of the Nation of Islam, numbers are one of the most important means of communicating. The manipulation of numbers discloses knowledge about the world and the role of man in it and followers routinely refer to Islam as mathematics because they believe that knowledge otherwise hidden from them could be revealed through detecting numerical patterns.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: One could argue that even a supernatural being set apart from human is a religious cosmology that the Nation of Islam rebukes in favor of a deeply material understanding of the world with the human recognizing the God in himself through knowledge passed down by Fard Muhammad and his messenger Elijah.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam conceives of human being as having the attributes of God, exhorting the followers to recognize God as the original black man as opposed to an abstract God hovering above in the skies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: NOI Cities in the United States

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam radically differs from traditional Muslim belief in a supernatural being who monitors human behavior. The specific point of difference is Nation's conception of God. Rather than an entity separate from human, God is conceived as a human, the original black man. Fard Muhammad is considered a black God who exhorted his messenger Elijah Muhammad to preach to the black Americans in Detroit and related deindustrializing urban cities in the United States about their divine status and imminent liberation from the false religions that had mollified them into believing in a supernatural being who restores peace and justice in an afterlife. Scholars such as Edward E. Curtis have written extensively about the Nation's anthropocentric understanding of God, noting critics of Elijah Muhammad who accused him of committing shirk for associating God with human being yet defending the Nation of Islam as nevertheless an Islamic religious tradition with a set of ritual practices that allowed African-Americans understand their predicament in the U.S. white colony. Historically, the Nation's rejection of a supernatural being who monitors human behavior as a separate entity draws upon the burgeoning Ahmadiyya movement which had similarly recognized Mirza Ghulam Ahmad as the reincarnation of God. The Ahmadiyya movement arose in the colonial milieu of the Punjab province in British subcontinent where Christian missionaries and church funded medical professionals had progressively taken over looking after the well-being of local communities, thereby weakening the religious authority of local Muslim healers. Mirza Ghulam was acutely aware of the power of modern western science in altering the nature of religious authority and sought to draw upon the insights of modern western science to reject the authority of the Christian missionaries of sciences and replace them with Islam. He took a page out of their playbook by sending his followers to North America to do mission work and preach about Islam as the basis of insights on health and healing advanced by modern western science. His message resonated with African-American migrants from the U.S. south who had experienced bouts of novel illnesses such as tuberculosis living in deindustrializing cities such as Detroit, leading to the emergence of new religious movements such as the Moorish Science Temple and the Nation of Islam. I would argue that the Nation of Islam ultimately replaces Christianity with Islam as the source of the imminent material well-being that was promised by modern western science. That is why it departs from traditional notions of Islam which may believe in a God monitoring human behavior, dismissing spiritual devotion to a separate God in favor of ritual practices one can do here and now. More scholarship needs to interrogate the relationship between biomedicine and the Nation of Islam to historically contextualize what makes the movement a religion and a form of Islam, yet nevertheless a challenge to how most Muslims and non-Muslims alike might understand the relationship between man and God in Islamic theology.

Reference: Robert Dannin. *Black Pilgrimage to Islam*. Oxford University Press on Demand. isbn: 9780195300246.

Reference: Herbert Berg. *Elijah Muhammad and Islam*. NYU Press. isbn: 9780814791134.

Reference: Patrick D. Bowen. *A History of Conversion to Islam in the United States, Volume 1*. BRILL. isbn: 9789004300699.

Reference: Richard Brent Turner. *Islam in the African-American Experience*. Indiana University Press. isbn: 9780253343239.

Reference: Kambiz GhaneaBassiri. *A History of Islam in America*. Cambridge University Press. isbn: 9781139788915.

Reference: Sally Howell. *Old Islam in Detroit*. Oxford University Press, USA. isbn: 9780199372003.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam routinely ascribes onto its leaders the honor of a messiah. Louis Farrakhan for instance has been compared to the biblical figure of Moses in Egypt, delivering his people out of enslavement of mind.

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, all the messiahs come in this lifetime as opposed to a life hereafter. They include figures such as Fard Muhammad, God incarnate who shared the hopeful message of attaining godly qualities to Elijah Muhammad, his messenger as well as Louis Farrakhan who has sustained the quest for making African-Americans realize their godlike qualities since the late seventies.

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam highly values numerology, the study of numbers, to calculate the coming of end times.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No, the messiah arrived in the form of a black man long before but then a mad scientist named Yacoub created the white man, thus initiating centuries of forgetfulness.

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam rejects the messiah in the Christian tradition who came once and will return someday again, arguing instead to find the messiah in our everyday life.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the messiah returns repeatedly in the Nation's cosmology since liberation unfolds here and now than a later time.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: In many ways, the messiah is a political leader. However he forms an alternative community within the current political system rather than attack it head on. Such a seemingly passive politics is the point of contestation between Elijah Muhammad and Malcolm X, with the latter seeking more engagement with the current political system not just nationally but also globally.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Notes: Yes, Elijah Muhammad was in many ways a priestly figure who restored Islam in North America. However he is referred to as a minister instead of a priest. Nonetheless, members of the Nation of Islam have treated with reverence that one expects for a priest and routinely draw upon his teachings in their ministry such as hip-hop artists and rappers whose lyrics are littered with speeches delivered by Elijah Muhammad.

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there are numerous norms prescribed by the Nation of Islam such as dressing plainly and maintaining gender segregation until marriage.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

Notes: Many members of the Nation of Islam routinely engage in practices that contradict the prescriptions of the movement yet do so when away from the religious gatherings. Converts are frequently urban dwellers who may have been attending night clubs and other public spaces that are considered immoral. Yet it would be naive to assume that upon converting to the Nation, they swiftly abandon those prior activities. As with followers of any other religious tradition, Nation's followers display an ambiguity to their ritual practices of piety.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam offers rationale for all of its moral norms by highlighting the imminent material benefits to the members. These benefits center around financial and mental independence from public assistance and improved work ethic.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: No, moral norms are linked to personal relationships that are dynamics and do not follow a static principle.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they are injunctions delivered by God who is also a man embodied by Fard Muhammad.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam ascribes its moral norms to the commands of Elijah Muhammad who they regard as a Prophet messiah as well as the commands of Fard Muhammad, God incarnate, as retold by Elijah. These commands have been archived in books such as Message to the Blackman in America.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: The Nation of Islam follows a deeply materialist metaphysics that builds on scientific knowledge about hygiene to facilitate African-Americans into gaining liberation from racial injustice. Norms such as shaving the beard for instance are considered moral for men in the Nation of Islam since a clean shaven man is supposed to limit contraction of infectious diseases.

Moral norms apply to:

- Only one gender
- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Norms apply to all members of the Nation of Islam, although some norms are gendered such as the injunction to shave the beard which applies to men. The Nation however does not distinguish African-Americans based on class even though its ritual practices attempt to demonstrate the efficacy of Islam in helping African-Americans create a nuclear family unit and engage in all sorts of practices such as dressing well and being punctual that one associates with middle-class professionals.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No, members are encouraged to browse for potential marriage partners through complex set of relationships with captains of the Fruits of Islam and Muslim Girls in Training, the two training groups separated by gender.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: Elijah Muhammad, the Nation's prophetic figure, had multiple wives, including but not limited to Clara Muhammad and Tynnetta Muhammad. As such, he is similar to Prophet Muhammad from 7th century Arabian peninsula who married multiple women such as Aisha after the death of his first wife Khadija. As a patriarchal religious movement, the Nation of Islam idealizes a form of black manhood that protects the family through discipline and hard work, and the wife in return promises to raise the next generation as leaders rather than dependents on public assistance.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, women in the Nation of Islam are expected to be married to only one man at a time. However, they might remarry after the death of their husbands. The Nation of Islam routinely attracts women converts who have recently lost a husband to either death or abandonment, hence the prospects for finding a marital partner who has a strong work ethic and desire to serve as a patriarch who can look after his family is a key benefit for aspiring women converts to the Nation.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: The Nation of Islam prescribes a set of conservative sexual norms including dressing plainly and covering the body. Various practices associated with urban youth such as clubbing, premarital sex, drinking are frowned upon as members undergo a process of both bodily and mental cleansing from the yearning for material stuff and pleasure that according to Warith Deen Muhammad, the leader of the reformed community and Elijah's youngest son, keeps one imprisoned by a ghetto mentality. Warith Deen reconfigured pleasure away from material riches to productive work, as exemplified by the image attached below of a woman who displays pleasure through showcasing her skills in mathematics and business that made it possible for her to work in a corporate setting successfully. Examples of sexual constraints for men specifically include abstinence from drinking, premarital sex, and drugs, all of which inculcate laziness, and they are overcome through rigorous training as members of the Fruits of Islam. Members for instance are threatened with expulsion from the Nation if they do not arrive at the Fruits of Islam meetings punctually.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: One of the most concerning sexual practice for women is premarital sex since such sexual arrangements may result in unwed mothers. Lacking financial assistance from a man, unwed mothers may find it necessary to abort their children, a practice the Nation frowns upon as an example of the government's attempt to limit the production of black babies and therefore an attempt to bar black women from raising future generation of black leaders. Even as the racially antagonistic theology of Elijah Muhammad such as belief in white man as a devil was tempered and reneged by his son Warith Deen, the sexual conservatism of the Nation did not recede. Followers of Warith Deen continued to warn women against the dangers of abortion and the various ways their motherhood is undermined including the designing of homes and appliances such as stairs and electrical outlets which may cause serious dangers to a young child.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: On the contrary, the Nation of Islam sees itself as a religious movement that could facilitate men into regaining their manhood from liberal promises of integration which effeminizes men into dependency on the redemptive force of whiteness.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, fasting is one of the key tenets of Islam and the Nation of Islam is no different. Members are exhorted to fast, deeming the practice as a medicinal injunction of the greatest doctor, the Almighty Allah. One of the main benefits the followers of Nation of Islam taut for fasting is discipline, arguing that discipline facilitates control over the hunger for food as well as seemingly less material desires such as love. Without discipline, society risks collapsing. As with other muslim communities, followers of the nation of islam are required to fast for an entire month and apart from refraining any food or drinks between dawn to dusk, they must also refrain from having sex. Among other benefits of fasting is the awakening of a libertarian politics. Unlike an authoritarian state that forcibly imposes discipline, the individual who fasts gains mastery over self-discipline and in the process maximizes the potential to resist dependency on or even desire for an authoritarian state.

Reference: Louis Farrakhan The significance and beauty of the month of Ramadan

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam has a detailed set of foods that followers are required to abstain. All of these food items were produced by enslaved Africans in the Americas. By ingesting them, the Nation argues, one remains in an enslaved state, incapable of remembering a past that predates the transatlantic slave trade. Such an embodied understanding of remembering and forgetfulness centered around the affect of food items we consume means that even tasty food such as soul dishes are taboo even though they are not necessarily classified as haram by other Muslim communities. To ensure that followers follow the prescribed diet, the Nation of Islam values the creation of independently run grocery stores where costumers are reminded of what they are supposed to eat.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No, members undergo a reversion to Islam through far less painful ritual practices including dress. It is assumed that reverts have already endured immense pain from living in the U.S. domestic colony as its racially black subjects. The Nation promises imminent liberation from pain through self-discipline.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No, members who fail to follow the disciplinary regulations get kicked out of the movement, a form of punishment potentially worse than physical flagellation since without the support of nation, they return to an urban setting where they are excessively reliant on the state and its public assistance.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No, on the contrary, members are exhorted to overcome their prior state of mental death through learning about Islam as their original religion. The Nation in other words seeks to awaken minds that had been dead for decades and centuries.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: No, property is considered valuable. The most valuable property is land. The Nation of Islam argues that ownership of land is critical for the project of gaining self-reliance and liberation from dependency on the state. As a movement started by migrants from the rural south, such an acute awareness of the powers one gains from having ownership of land makes a lot of sense. Clara Muhammad for instance was raised in a farm home. Even though her father did not own the land, he nonetheless cultivated it in return for living on it for free. The urban setting of Detroit where homes were crowded and there was very little open space for work and leisure differed markedly, thus making Clara deeply unimpressed by the promises of uplift from migrating to the north. In many ways, the Nation of Islam is an attempt to overcome the illness of life in urban cities, and the source of that illness is lack of access to land.

Reference: James Baldwin. Letter from a region in my mind. The New Yorker.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, members are required to attend temple for religious worship and even more important than the time spent at the temple for worship is meetings organized by the captains of the Fruits of Islam and Muslim Girls in Training for the newly recruited male and female members of the Nation of Islam. The Fruits of Islam for instance would last from morning to evening, with the captains teaching the recruits various skills deemed critical for managing the home such as sewing, dress designing, knitting and needlework. After 8 pm, the sisters would begin the "secretarial classes", also described as "typing drills." An older sister would write an English word on the blackboard. The younger sisters would proceed to translate that word in their notebooks. Although such tasks were gendered and deemed valuable primarily for their maternal qualities, graduates routinely credit the long hours they spent undergoing such arduous drills for learning how to work independently and establish self-run businesses. One of the areas where women graduates have made the greatest contribution to is fashion design. Carmen Muhammad for instance built on her years of training as member of Muslim Girls in Training to establish an independent fashion design industry that she named Al-Nisa (arabic for woman) and competes in international competitions where she gets to juxtapose conventional fashion designs with her distinctly designs that combine beauty with modesty.

Reference: Ebony Muhammad Safiyyah. Islamic Fashion Weekend 2016: The Ultimate Takeover of the Fashion Industry. The Final Call.

Reference: . Musli designer wins prestigious awards at Torino Fashion Week. Final Call News.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Members take the risk of imagining a new family built through marrying their peers and in the process potentially distancing from their prior families, many of whom might be of Christian background and look at their new found enthusiasm for Islam suspiciously. Additional physical risks include undergoing a complete bodily transformation by wearing sets of dresses that are plain and markedly differ from the kinds of clothing they may have worn otherwise.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam has detailed sets of ethical injunctions against premarital sex, drinking, taking drugs, all centered around overcoming a ghetto mentality that has for centuries disabled African-Americans from remembering a past that predates the transatlantic slave trade and amidst forgetfulness constantly depend on the U.S nation-state and its state apparatus for survival.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Out group members routinely marginalize members of the Nation of Islam. They range from non-Muslim observers, especially journalists and sociologists who during the late fifties and early sixties produce sensationalist narratives of the Nation of Islam as a political movement that produces hate to counter white anti-black hate to traditional Muslims who might draw on textual sources in the Islamic tradition, namely the Quran and the Hadith, to create a wedge between the black experience in the Americas with Islam. Scholars such as Suad Abdul Khabeer, Zareena Grewal and Jamillah Karim have written extensively on the marginalization of the Nation of Islam from fellow Muslims, arguing that the dismissal of the Nation of Islam as heretical exemplifies a form of ethnocentrism in which Islam is mapped onto the Middle-east and any form of Islam that arises within a geographical setting such as North America therefore lacks the necessary doctrinal rigor to be considered as authentically Islamic. The common thread across both types of marginalization is a resistance against recognizing the Nation of Islam as a religious movement, thus demonstrating the stakes at distinguishing religion from politics.

Reference: Edward Curtis E.. Islamizing the Black Body: Ritual and Power in Elijah Muhammad's Nation of Islam. *Religion and American Culture: A Journal of Interpretation*, 12(2)

Reference: Su'ad Abdul Khabeer. *Muslim Cool*. NYU Press. isbn: 9781479894505.

Reference: E. Essien-Udom U.. *Black Nationalism: A Search for an Identity in America*. University of Chicago Press.

Reference: C. Eric Lincoln. *The Black Muslims in America*. isbn: 9780865433991.

Reference: Sherman A. Jackson. *Islam and the Blackamerican*. Oxford University Press on Demand. isbn: 9780195180817.

Reference: Jamillah Karim. *American Muslim Women: Negotiating Race, Class, and Gender Within the Ummah*. NYU Press. isbn: 9780814748091, 0814748090.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 24

Notes: The Nation of Islam feminized religion, meaning it gave plenty of opportunities for women to acquire religious piety through small-scale ritual practices centered around managing the home. By restoring a family unit for black Americans whereby the men would financially look after the family and the women would look after the home, the Nation made it possible for women to confine all of their ritual practices within the realm of the home, ranging from cooking to dressing to cleaning. Hence, it would be safe to argue that small-scale ritual practices are not set apart for a particular time period but rather are integrated in the totality of life, especially for women followers as they consolidate the Nation's idealized black motherhood as nurturing, protective, and most importantly industrious partners of male patriarchs.

Reference: Dawn-Marie Gibson. *The Nation of Islam, Louis Farrakhan, and the Men Who Follow Him*. Springer. isbn: 9781137530844.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50

Notes: Nation's large scale ritual practices include temple attendance, drill sessions at the Fruits of Islam and Muslim Girls in Training, as well as school attendance for children between elementary to high school ages who attend the Sister Clara Muhammad Schools.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 0.5

Notes: The Nation's large scale ritual practices are rigorous, following set times. Hence it would be rare for the time between performances to last much longer than half and hour.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: Although scholars have routinely studied the Nation of Islam as a textual tradition through extensive study of Elijah Muhammad's injunctions in his writings, I would argue that the Nation of Islam is less focused on orthodoxy and more on orthopraxis since it aspires to facilitate an emotional conversion from a state of shame to pride in black man and womanhood rather than immerse followers in the scriptural sources in the Islamic tradition. Even though followers of the Nation of Islam have gone abroad to study the Islamic tradition extensively, they have sought to draw on such educational experiences to build transnational networks rather than to educate fellow followers on what they need to know about Islam.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam has various orthopraxy checks that transpire across face to face interactions as exemplified by the guard duties conducted by members of the Fruits of Islam at the door of the temple to ensure that the sisters attending the Muslim Girls in Training sessions are able to enter the temple safely yet also confirm that the sisters were dressed properly. Such orthodoxy checks gave a rhythm to new converts' urban life with one member crediting such duties for ensuring that he remained busy all week long and only had weekends to spend time with friends.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, for instance members fast during the month of ramadan which repeats every year during a specific time.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: As in other Islamic traditions, the use of intoxicants is strongly prohibited in the Nation of Islam. However, it would be naive to assume that followers strictly follow the prescriptions against the use of intoxicants and other things such as drugs. Gerald Early recalls befriending brothers from the Nation of Islam who would return to their apartments after Fruits of Islam training sessions and break out into smoking marijuana. While failing to abide by the doctrinal injunctions of Elijah Muhammad, they nevertheless reiterated their respect for him and confirmed his prophetic status, thus demonstrating that the charisma of the man and his overall message of bodily and mental liberation from enslavement was far more valuable than the introduction of new doctrines about Islam.

Reference: Edward Curtis IV E.. Islamizing the Black Body: Ritual and Power in Elijah Muhammad's Nation of Islam. *Religion and American Culture: A Journal of Interpretation*, 12(2)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam does not encourage followers to tattoo, exhorting them instead to seek bodily cleanliness from such dirt. The word integration however is tattooed on the chest of a white woman as depicted in a cartoon, with the white woman embodying the empty allure of liberation through legal reforms such as racial integration.

Reference: Edward E. Curtis IV. *Black Muslim Religion in the Nation of Islam, 1960-1975*. Univ of North Carolina Press. isbn: 9780807877449.

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Notes: Unlike other Muslim communities, the Nation of Islam do not value circumcision as a critical rite of initiation for new born into Islam.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, food items that are historically traceable to the coerced enslavement of Africans such as soul food are taboos, with the argument that ingesting them would further impede one from remembering a past that predates that historical period.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the male Nation's followers are required to comb their hair and cut it to a length that makes them look professional and upright while the women followers are advised to grow their hair long yet keep it clothed as opposed to exposed. Many converts routinely credit the aesthetics of "looking sharp" for drawing them to the Nation of Islam. Instead of being persuaded by doctrine, they were persuaded instead by the promise of a physical transformation of bodily parts including the hair and in the process set apart from conventional representations of the black urban poor.

Reference: America's Islamic Heritage Museum Discussion with Clara Muhammad's Granddaughters

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, male members are required to wear pants and shirt, often dressed as a military officer, and women are required to wear loose pants that are plain and modest. Although the most dress encouraged by the Nation is routinely represented as simply black and white, followers routinely add color to their modest dresses as exemplified by the clothing designs of Carmen Muhammad.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam discourages the collection of ornaments, exhorting its followers instead to maintain plainness and modesty across their bodies and the spaces they inhabit such as the home.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

Notes: No, members of the Nation of Islam speak English. Rather than language, they invest in the knowledge of numbers to gain insight into hidden knowledge.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Shaving. Men are required to shave, with beards deemed responsible for the spread of contagious diseases.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: No, members routinely refer to one another as brothers and sisters to express their commitment to an extended family constituted by shared commitment to Islam. Followers of Warith Deen Muhammad's reformed group started to in the early eighties identify as Bilalians, remembering collectively an African man named Bilal who was appointed by the Prophet Muhammad from 7th century Arabia as the person in charge of making call to prayer of the nascent Muslim community. By identifying as Bilalians, they sought to both confirm their commitment to a form of global Islam that extends beyond the much more nationalistic vision of Elijah Muhammad to create independent insulate black Muslim urban communities while simultaneously reinforce the Nation's commitment to an afro-centric Islam against tendencies among Muslims in general and scholars in particular to overemphasize Islam's relationship to territories such as Middle-east and South Asia as oppose to Africa.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Nation of Islam is best characterized as a nation within the United States, since followers are encouraged to form communities that function independently from governmental assistance yet do not necessarily aspire to replace the government through any active political means.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam lacks an institution that operates with the sole purpose of offering famine relief. Yet the movement does provide institutional support for its followers to purchase food and drinks that follow its prescriptions for bodily and mental health. These institutions include grocery stores that are run independently by the Nation of Islam as well as farms bought by the Nation's leaders.

Reference: Starla Muhammad. Nation of Islam Michigan Farm hosts agriculture seminar. Final Call.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, members may seek for famine relief through contacting nationally operating charities such as Feeding America but examples of such requests are largely absent online.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, it aims to uplift followers from bodily and mental poverty of relying extensively on public assistance for food, education, and housing in urban settings.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but the Nation aspires to redress poverty through establishing independently run grocery stores and farms, thus making it possible for followers to overcome dependency on other organizations.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: No, but the Nation of Islam values strong nuclear families and a maternal figure at home who could look after not only the children but also the elderly and the infirm.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but the Nation of Islam discourages followers to rely on state run institutions such as hospice and nursing homes, and exhorts them instead to transform their homes into stations where the elderly might seek relief.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam provides education to its adherents through institutions such as the Fruits of Islam and the Muslim Girls in Training for adults and Sister Clara Muhammad Schools for adolescents. All of these educational institutions share their genesis in the University of Al-Islam, which began as a homeschool held inside the home of Clara Muhammad on Hasting Street, Detroit as well as on the top floor of Carlisle theatre that once used to exist on this historical street demolished and replaced by a highway in the fifties.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: no, anyone may join the Sister Clara Muhammad schools that offer formal education to children between the K-12 age groups. Yet, presently, the network of Sister Clara Muhammad Schools in the Americas (37 in continental America and 1 in Bermuda) struggle for financial solvency and therefore are as much in need for student enrollment among followers of the movement as they would be for others.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, male and female adherents receive extra-religious education by joining the Fruits of Islam and the Muslim girls in Training where they learn a range of skills related to home management and security that are deemed critical for the development of a black nuclear family with a male head and female manager.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Nation of Islam has a large concentration of followers in the south side of Chicago and Atlanta. Mosque Maryam on 73rd and Stony Island Chicago remains an important site where followers gather for worship and religious education. Residents from surrounding neighborhoods also routinely encounter male members of the Fruit of Islam distributing the Nation's newspaper Final Call with commentaries of Elijah Muhammad on recent political developments.

Reference: Luke White. What Must be Done: As Its leader loses national relevance, the Nation of Islam struggles to stay visible on the South Side. Southside Weekly.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they interact with local police, social workers, and the mayor's office but do so in order to wrestle away any dependency on such institutional bureaucracies. From safety to education, the

Nation has played a key role offering services to African-Americans in urban settings such as Chicago's south side. Even though the rationale motivating their efforts is a deep suspicion of state run bureaucracies for instilling a mentality of dependency, figure heads of the local government such as the former mayor of Chicago Rahm Emmanuel praised the Nation for alleviating the burden of state-run bureaucracies in looking after the well-being of the region's residents.

Reference: Armstrong Williams. The Nation of Islam Could be Chicago's Savior. The Hill.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: No, the Nation of Islam lacks the capacity for storing food for public and instead invests its energies on ensuring that its members are able to access fresh foods and vegetables.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as exemplified by the Salvation Army. However the Nation strives to limit its followers dependency on such institutions.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: No, the Nation relies on the local government for such services.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: yes, by the local government of cities such as Chicago for instance.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: No, members walk and take the bus and avail any other forms of transportation provided by the local government.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, by the local government. Examples include public buses, subways, and trains.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The Nation does not levy taxes but nevertheless relies on the financial contribution of its members for its sustenance. Critics have argued that the Nation's present-day Louis Farrakhan routinely exploits the very poor he seeks to uplift, citing numerous examples of mismanaged organizations that were established by him including the failure to pay property taxes to the state.

Reference: David Jackson , William Gaines. The power and the money. Chicago Tribune.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The local government levies property taxes on the properties that the Nation owns.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the male members of the Fruits of Islam routinely serve as a police force, and have been accredited for maintaining safety in the Chicago's south side, while the Chicago Police stays away.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Chicago Police for example. However, the Nation ensures that such interactions are kept at a minimum and even evaded through training its male members to provide the policing instead.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the penal system of the United States of America.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: However, there has been unverified theories that Malcolm X was murdered by a member of the Nation of Islam who was hired by the FBI.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: But members of the Nation of Islam have been kicked out of the movement. Most well-known example of an exiled member is Malcolm X.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Malcolm X is a good example of a former member of the Nation of Islam ostracized for his criticism of Elijah Muhammad's leadership and desire for greater involvement with Muslims and non-Muslims abroad in forming a political movement for resistance against colonial control across the world.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Members of the Nation of Islam are expected to consolidate the injunctions made by their leader Louis Farrakhan and former leader Elijah Muhammad. However there isn't a legal code enshrined in text. Many such as Wael Hallaq have argued that the Islamic tradition more broadly lacks a static legal code to be implemented the same way regardless of time and place.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: However, members routinely engage in military drills to learn discipline and cultivate a strong man and womanhood.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No, members have often resisted participating in the United States military as exemplified by Elijah Muhammad for instance who was imprisoned for evading the draft during World War II and Mohammad Ali who likewise questioned why he should serve a country that has oppressed him during the hey day of Vietnam War.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The United States military is responsible for protecting American citizens including members of the Nation of Islam.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They can learn english by attending the public schools for instance.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Nation of Islam has an extensive list of important dates on the calendar that are as follows: Savior's Day, February 26th for celebrating the birthday of W. Fard Muhammad and Savior's Day, October 7th for celebrating the birthday of Elijah Muhammad. The latter was instituted in 1985 for followers who were too young to recall Fard Muhammad. Holy Day of Reconciliation October 16th These important dates have been deemed religious by the United States penal system as well, allowing NOI inmates relief from work on those dates.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Nation of Islam has independently operated grocery stores as well as farms for the production of small and large scale agriculture.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Outside the food services offered by the Nation, members are left with the global supply of food chain that makes it way to urban grocery stores and dollar stores that are often less healthier and more prone to causing all sorts of illnesses such as heart disease and diabetes.

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